

Review Article

Thermodynamic strategies to increase solubility for higher energy density in organic redox flow batteries

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ABSTRACT

Improving the solubility of redox-active organic molecules (ROMs) in electrolyte solutions is vital for boosting the energy density of redox flow batteries and avoiding precipitation issues. This study explores six thermodynamic strategies to enhance ROM solubility by lowering melting points or activity coefficients. Minor structural changes—such as tuning alkyl side chains, repositioning functional groups, or altering ROM ligands—introduce molecular asymmetry, consistently increasing solubility and energy density in various electrolyte solutions. Furthermore, tailored co-solvents or salting-in agents strengthen solute–solvent interactions, reducing activity coefficients. COSMO-RS proves effective for qualitatively assessing these modifications. These strategies collectively offer a structured approach to designing molecules and selecting solvent additives, optimizing ROM solubility and elevating battery performance.

1. Introduction

The rapid progress in solar and wind energy generation technologies has facilitated the widespread adoption of renewable energy production [1]. This advancement necessitates the development of Energy Storage Systems (ESSs) to address the inherent intermittency of these sources [2]. Electrochemical batteries present an efficient ESS alternative, bridging the gap between renewable energy generation and consumption. With their high energy density, conventional solid-state batteries are usually suitable for small to medium-scale applications. However, Redox Flow Batteries (RFBs) offer a more favorable cost-benefit ratio for large-scale applications due to their separation of energy and power, despite their lower energy density [3,4].

Currently, vanadium-based RFBs exhibit the highest level of technological readiness among RFBs. The lifespan, cost, and energy density of all-vanadium RFBs make this technology competitive against other mature batteries. However, its limited global abundance, high cost constrain its commercial viability, although its moderate energy density is less of a concern for stationary applications where the overall site footprint can be competitive with Li-ion installations. [3]. As a result, much attention has been focused on substituting vanadium species with redox-active organic molecules (ROMs) [5]. ROMs' scalability, along

with their potential for cost-effectiveness and safety in certain cases, make them attractive for large-scale energy storage applications, although these factors must be carefully evaluated for each specific ROM due to variability in synthesis costs and safety profiles. ROMs can be synthesized from abundant hydrocarbon sources, allowing for mass production without facing the resource or processing limits that affect other battery materials, such as metals [4]. This scalability means that ROMs can be produced without a significant increase in cost per unit, making them ideal candidates for grid-scale energy storage. Additionally, the synthesis processes of some ROMs can be simpler and less expensive compared to those for certain metals and rare minerals used in other battery technologies, which may help reduce costs, though this varies depending on the specific ROM and synthesis method. These ROMs must fulfill certain requirements to become commercially successful, such as being cost-effective and (electro-) chemically stable.

Unlike solid-state batteries, where redox-active species are in solid form, in RFBs these species are dissolved in an electrolyte solution, which circulates through the electrochemical cell and are stored in large external tanks. Thus, for any newly proposed ROM, managing its solubility in the electrolyte throughout the charge and discharge processes of RFBs becomes a crucial requirement. Moreover, the development of strategies to enhance the solubility of redox-active species becomes

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necessary to advance the commercial viability of RFBs. This enhancement in solubility would lead to higher charge density, reduced material costs, and potentially higher energy density if the cell potential difference is maintained or increased, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable and resilient energy infrastructure.

Recent reviews have presented chemical and heuristic approaches to enhance the solubility of redox-active species [3–6]. However, the lack of a deep understanding of the thermodynamic phenomena governing the solubilization of ROMs has led to slow technological developments, eventually in the wrong direction.

This study presents a systematic approach to applying six thermodynamic strategies aimed at enhancing the solubility of ROMs in electrolyte solutions, thereby supporting the development of high-energy-density batteries. Key thermodynamic properties that govern ROM solubility are rigorously analyzed, and targeted strategies are proposed to modify and tailor them. Thermodynamic principles are explained via simple applications to allow non-experts to understand and apply the strategies to their systems.

The COSMO-RS predictive model is utilized to guide the assessment and selection of some of these six strategies, effectively reducing experimental time and resource requirements while enabling the pre-evaluation of a broader range of modifications and materials. All strategies presented are supported by theoretical foundations, with critical analyses to enhance their practical applicability. This study serves as a guide to advancing battery technology by increasing energy density through improved ROM solubility.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Thermodynamics

Solubility can be related to changes in Gibbs energy (ΔG), expressed through variations in enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) during phase transitions. The enthalpic term represents heat or internal energy changes, reflecting energy interactions within each phase. The entropic term quantifies the system's energy distribution, associated with the degree of disorder or randomness in each phase. Given that most ROMs are solid under conventional battery operating conditions, they must be solubilized in electrolyte solutions. This process can be described as a solid-liquid equilibrium, illustrated in Eq. (1) [7].

$$\Delta G_{sol} = \Delta H_{sol} - T\Delta S_{sol} = 0 \quad (1)$$

While this equation provides a basic understanding of solubility (solid-liquid equilibrium), it lacks practical insights. From this concept, Eq. (2) can be developed to better describe the solubility of a solute in a solvent [7]. This equation relates the solubility of a compound i (x_i) at a given temperature (T) with some of its measurable thermophysical properties, namely its melting temperature (T_m) and enthalpy of melting (ΔH_m), its change in heat capacity upon melting (Δc_p), and the liquid phase non-ideality expressed through its activity coefficient (γ_i):

$$\ln(x_i\gamma_i) = \frac{\Delta H_m}{RT} \left(\frac{T}{T_m} - 1 \right) + \frac{\Delta c_p}{R} \left[\ln \left(\frac{T_m}{T} \right) - \frac{T_m}{T} + 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

Since the change in heat capacity upon fusion (Δc_p) is usually small compared to the melting enthalpy term, it is often neglected in solubility calculations [8,9]. This approach was used in this work to analyze the effects presented here. The simplified representation of solid-liquid equilibrium, shown in Eq. (3), offers a practical understanding of the variables involved in solubilizing solid ROMs in a liquid electrolyte. Additionally, increasing the temperature should generally increase the solubility of ROMs, except in unconventional systems where simplifications could not be applied, such as those of co-crystal formation may occur [10].

$$x_i = \frac{\exp \left(\frac{\Delta H_m}{RT} \left(\frac{T}{T_m} - 1 \right) \right)}{\gamma_i} \quad (3)$$

For readers less familiar with thermodynamics, solid solubilization in a liquid solvent can be conceptualized as a two-step sequence. The first step involves melting the solid solute, characterized by the enthalpy of melting (ΔH_m) and the melting temperature (T_m). The lower the value of these properties, the more easily the solid can be transformed into a liquid. In the second step, the two liquids are mixed, and the energies involved can be quantified through the activity coefficient (γ), which correlates with the Gibbs free energy involved in the mixing step. Therefore, the solubility of a solid ROM is correlated with the energies of its melting and mixing with the solvent, as shown in Eq. (3). Thus, any modification that reduces ROMs melting properties (ΔH_m , and T_m) or activity coefficients (γ) would enhance their solubility (x). The six modifications herein evaluated target reducing either ΔH_m , and T_m or γ .

2.2. Assessing solubility: experimental and predictive approaches

For accurately predicting the solubility of solid redox-active organic molecules in solution, knowledge of both the activity coefficient and melting properties is essential, as outlined in Eq. (3). Experimentally, these properties can be measured using specific methods. Melting properties, such as melting temperature and enthalpy, are typically measured via calorimetry. For activity coefficients, solid-liquid equilibrium approaches [11] are generally the most suitable, especially for ROMs. Using SLE, one can determine the activity coefficient from solubility data, provided the melting properties are known.

In cases where experimental data on melting properties and activity coefficients are unavailable, predictive tools provide valuable alternatives. Melting properties are challenging to predict accurately due to their dependence on lattice energy and specific crystal structure, and only limited approaches are suitable. Machine learning (ML) models have shown potential here, offering insights through large datasets [12]. However, ML approaches require extensive experimental data for training, are generally limited to the scope of the available data and present a steep learning curve for practical implementation. Given these constraints, ML is less accessible as a routine tool for melting property prediction. Activity coefficients, on the other hand, can be effectively estimated using COSMO-based models such as COSMO-RS (Conductor-like Screening Model for Real Solvents) [13–15] and COSMO-SAC, which offer reliable accuracy and user-friendly interfaces (e.g., COSMOTherm [16] and JCOSMO [17]).

The modification of ROMs or electrolytes can be efficiently guided by the principles of the strategies here presented. From a practical perspective, the assessment of the intended modifications targeting melting property reduction could be done heuristically when experimental data is not available. Subsequently, a reliable COSMO based predictive approach should be employed to evaluate the influence of melting properties strategies on activity coefficient, and to assess strategies targeting activity coefficient reduction. This approach allows for practical efficient screening of modification before evaluation on experimental solubility. Therefore, helping to optimize the search for high energy density batteries.

It is important to note that the activity coefficient of each species varies with concentration. At saturation (maximum solubility) activity coefficients diverge from values observed at lower concentrations. In this study, we focus on the activity coefficient at infinite dilution (γ^∞ , where $x_{ROM} \approx 0$), which offers qualitative but reliable insights into solute-solvent interactions. The infinite dilution activity coefficient serves as an efficient screening metric, ideal for evaluating preliminary strategies and identifying promising ROM derivatives, additives, and solvents. This choice allows for a streamlined, thermodynamically consistent approach to evaluating solubility without necessitating the

full determination of saturation values, which may not be practical or required for initial screening purposes. The use of the infinite dilution coefficient thus aligns with the study's goal to offer an accessible yet rigorous metric to evaluate solubility enhancements in ROM systems.

2.3. COSMO-RS

The COSMO-RS (Conductor-like Screening Model for Real Solvents) [13–15] model was used in this study as a qualitatively reliable and straightforward approach to predicting activity coefficients in systems containing ions [18] and redox-active organic molecules [19]. The accuracy of the model has been extensively validated in the past, with, for example, experimental solubility data of systems containing ILS in water [20], organic solutes in ILS [21], and aqueous electrolytes [22]. A comparison of over 41,000 data points for infinite dilution activity coefficients across 233 ILS, 150 molecular solutes, and 8554 distinct binary systems demonstrated that COSMO-RS provides consistent qualitative accuracy across a broad range of ionic strengths and solvent environments. The dataset encompasses activity coefficients spanning several orders of magnitude, reaching values as high as 10,000, further confirming the model's reliability in capturing solute–solvent interactions in complex ionic systems [23].

COSMO-RS treats the solvent as a continuum dielectric medium and uses the distribution of surface charge densities (σ -profiles or sigma profiles) over the surface of molecules to anticipate intermolecular interactions. These profiles offer a detailed characterization of the polarity and electrostatic nature of the surface of molecules. By analyzing the interactions between the surface charges of the solute and solvent, COSMO-RS can predict how molecules interact in a mixture, thus determining the activity coefficients of each component.

The sigma profiles used in this work were generated from the structural and electronic optimization of molecules. All geometry optimizations and charge density calculations were performed with the software package TURBOMOLE [24], through its interface TMoleX v.4.5 [25], using density functional theory (DFT) with the BP86 functional and the triple zeta valence polarization with diffuse functions (def2-TZVPD) basis set [25]. Molecular surface cavities were constructed using the novel “FINE” approach (fine grid marching tetrahedron cavity [26]), which creates a COSMO surface whose segments are more uniform and evenly distributed compared to the standard COSMO cavity. The configuration of those quantum chemistry calculations corresponds to that of the “BP-TZVPD-FINE_21” parametrization of COSMO-RS, available in the software package COSMOTerm v.21 [16]. This parametrization presents other advantages over classical COSMO-RS levels TZVP or DMOL³, such as improvements in the hydrogen bonding and van der Waals dispersion term and a correction for residual dielectric charge (RDC) [27,28]. This parameter set is considered to offer the best quality predictions among those available in COSMOTerm [16,29].

The charge density distribution for ions was calculated separately for each ionic species, excluding ROMs. This means that sigma profiles for neutral and ionic species were determined individually. This approach reduces the number of possible conformers and generally yields high accuracy, especially for dissociated species [30]. Although charged ROMs should be dissociated especially on diluted aqueous solutions, a previous study [19] reported high accuracy on representing ROMs as ion pairs, where the energetic optimization of charges was performed with the ions together.

Activity coefficient models such as COSMO-RS cannot independently predict the solubilities of solids in liquid solutions when melting property data is not available. As such, the predictive capability of COSMO-RS for this studied case was assessed through partition coefficient (K) comparisons in biphasic systems using flow battery electrolytes formed with ionic liquid and polymers, as presented in Fig. 1. The partition coefficient is calculated from the ratio of ROM concentrations in each phase. Therefore, K could be estimated only from their activity

Fig. 1. Comparison of COSMO-RS Predictions and experimental partition coefficients (K) [19] for viologen derivatives in electrolyte biphasic systems.

coefficients if Eq. (3) is applicable; not requiring the knowledge of their melting properties. Thus, making them a practical choice for validating COSMO-RS in this context.

The biphasic systems used here for validation (Fig. 1) formed without polymers are significantly more complex than typical battery electrolytes. Containing up to six different ions in equilibrium (NH_4^+ , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- , Br^- , $[\text{P}_{44414}]^+$, and a viologen derivative cation). The presence of water as the solvent in both phases adds another layer of complexity. The complex long-range interactions involved in the liquid-liquid equilibrium of these electrolytes, containing six ions and water, resulted in a correlation coefficient of 0.65 (Fig. 1). Despite the apparently low quantitative accuracy, COSMO-RS consistently demonstrated high qualitative accuracy in predicting the partition coefficients of viologen derivatives, as evidenced by the correct prediction of phase partitioning for all species in all systems studied. A similar conclusion was also reported for multi-ion aqueous biphasic systems (ABS) prepared with viologen and ferrocyanide [31]. Considering that the systems studied in this manuscript are much less complex, lower deviations are expected.

Fig. 2 compares COSMO-RS infinite dilution activity coefficients (γ^∞) with the solubility of quinone and viologen derivatives in water. While γ^∞ provides qualitative insights into solute-solvent interactions, solubility also depends on melting properties (T_m and ΔH_m). Note that melting properties are not predicted by COSMO-RS and, when relevant in this work, were sourced from experimental results published in the literature. Additionally, γ^∞ assumes infinite dilution, excluding concentration effects. Despite these limitations, a clear correlation is observed between γ^∞ and solubility trends, indicating that γ^∞ is a valuable qualitative tool for screening ROM solubility.

This result suggests that COSMO-RS effectively guides activity

Fig. 2. Comparison between COSMO-RS-predicted activity coefficients and experimental aqueous solubilities of viologens [32–34] and anthraquinones [35].

coefficient predictions but should be used cautiously for full solubility estimates, as it captures only one component of the solubility equation (Eq. (3)). Thus, COSMO-RS is recommended for screening activity coefficient strategies, while heuristic guidelines should guide melting property modifications.

2.4. Practical applications

Increasing ROMs solubility by the herein proposed strategies application may not necessarily promote an enhancement on practical applications. Careful interpretation of thermodynamic principles, and risks involved on these strategies application are also essential to avoid misinterpretation and unwanted results.

An incorrect or limited understanding of thermodynamic fundamentals or the purpose of the strategies presented here can lead to misinterpretations, inaccurate correlations, and ineffective outcomes. For example, studies have incorrectly correlated the solubility of sulfaguanidine (SG) with boiling temperature and viscosity, assuming these parameters reflect polarity and interactions [36]. However, neither boiling temperature nor viscosity directly correlates with solubility. Other studies [37,38] attributed increases in solubility to the reduction of solvent viscosity, which is also incorrect. The reduction of viscosity affects mass transfer, which can enhance kinetics and speed up the reaching of thermodynamic equilibrium by the mixture. However, it does not alter the solubility itself. These misinterpretations underscore the importance of correctly understanding the fundamental thermodynamic principles of solubilization for adequate design of ROMs.

Increasing ROM solubility can also raise the risk of unwanted side or parasitic reactions, potentially reducing battery efficiency or generating solids under operational conditions. Although these reactions fall outside the scope of this study, they must be considered in practical battery applications. Structural modifications or additive incorporation may introduce new decomposition pathways, requiring careful evaluation to ensure long-term stability. The strategies presented here aim to enhance solubility and, consequently, energy density in batteries. ROMs exist in both charged and uncharged states during battery operation, and these strategies are most effective when focused on the species with the lowest solubility in the electrolyte. The charge density and molecular structure of ROMs vary by charge state, influencing melting properties, solvent interactions, and activity coefficients—e.g., charged species favor polar solvents like water, while uncharged species interact better with less polar solvents. Although high solubility for both charge states is desirable, prioritizing the one with the lowest solubility should maximize the impact of these strategies. As discussed, COSMO-RS provides high qualitative accuracy in predicting activity coefficients for a range of ionic species, offering a reliable basis for evaluating unstable charged forms of ROMs. In cases where experimental quantification of unstable charging states is impractical, using a stable charging state of the same ROM as a qualitative model may provide valuable insights into strategy efficacy.

This study investigates 6 strategies to increase the solubility of ROMs. However, it does not examine their effects on ROMs synthesis, scalability, or performance under extreme conditions, such as variations in temperature and pressure. While increased solubility may offer potential benefits, it could also introduce challenges related to synthesis—particularly for approaches involving molecular structure modifications—as well as scalability and ionic synergy in practical RFB applications. Thus, the costs and complexities of developing new synthesis routes for modified ROMs may outweigh the advantages gained from improved solubility. To assess the feasibility of these strategies for large-scale battery production, comprehensive cost-benefit analyses and scalability studies are necessary.

Given that the type of solubility (solid in a liquid solvent) examined in this work is governed by solid-liquid equilibrium, which depends on the Gibbs energy of the solid solute and that of the liquid solution, it is not significantly affected by pressure, barring extreme conditions.

Regardless, the qualitative ranking of solubilities among different solutes does not change with pressure. Moreover, the strategies presented that rely on increasing solubility by decreasing activity coefficients lead to a second advantage: systems become more stable (or less prone to crystallization) at low temperatures. This melting temperature depression becomes more significant as the activity coefficient of the solute decreases. Notwithstanding these considerations, future research should explore the solubility of ROMs under extreme conditions (e.g., low temperatures or high pressures). The dynamics of ionic synergies in multi-component electrolytes is briefly explored in Section 3.2; however, to ensure their applicability across diverse operating environments detailed studies must be performed to each system.

3. Melting properties

Carnelley [39] established, as early as 1882, a relationship between molecular configurations and melting temperatures. Organic molecules with high asymmetric and flexible structures tend to present lower melting temperatures. Symmetrical molecules, due to their propensity for efficient packing, often form more stable lattices, influencing their melting temperatures primarily through entropic effects rather than enthalpic. Conversely, asymmetric molecules, which tend to poorly pack due to their irregular shapes, result in less stable lattices [40]. This instability results in decreases of the melting properties (T_m and ΔH_m) and, consequently, an increase in their solubilities as postulated by Eq. (3). Since the battery's charging and discharging cycles produce species with different interactions with the solvent—and thus different solubilities—the use of asymmetry-inducing strategies remains relevant. These strategies can be applied with only minor modifications to the ROM's molecular structure, whether in its charged or uncharged state. Consequently, the induction of asymmetry in the molecular structure of ROMs offers a promising approach to mitigate issues related to solid precipitation that may arise during charge and discharge cycles. Since charging or discharging the battery produces significantly different species, each with distinct interactions with the solvent and, consequently, different solubilities, the application of asymmetry-inducing strategies remains effective. These strategies require only minor modifications to the molecular structure of the ROM, regardless of whether it is in a charged or uncharged state. Consequently, it offers a promising approach to mitigate issues related to low solubility, such as low energy density or solid precipitation that may arise during charge and discharge cycles.

Subsequent experimental studies further reinforced correlations between ΔH_m , and T_m of organic solutes with their solubilities in several solvents. Treiner et al. [41] examined barbituric acid derivatives, establishing a direct correlation between the melting enthalpy and the aqueous solubility of these compounds. Xu et al. [42] explored the impact of cations and anions on the melting properties of quaternary onium salts and their solubilities in ethylene carbonate (EC) and dimethyl carbonate (DMC) solvents.

A significant benefit of employing redox-active organometallic or organic molecules in battery applications lies in the tunability of their molecular structures. Structural modifications of ROMs can affect their melting properties and interactions. The three strategies presented within this section focus on increasing the solubility of ROMs by reducing ΔH_m , and T_m . This can be achieved by imposing asymmetry on the chemical structure of ROMs via modification on side alkyl chains (Asymmetry by alkylation), changing functional group or ligands (Asymmetry by functionalization), or rearranging the pattern by which radicals are inserted (Asymmetry by substitution pattern).

3.1. Asymmetry by alkylation

Controlling the length of the alkyl chain moieties in ROMs allows for the modulation of their melting properties and, thus solubilities. Increasing the length of alkyl chains, even in symmetric ammonium-

based salts/ionic liquids, has been shown to systematically lower melting temperatures, according to the sequence $[N_{1111}]X > [N_{2222}]X > [N_{3333}]X > [N_{4444}]X$, regardless of the halogen anions X^- [11]. The T_m reduction can be correlated with the increase in the aqueous solubilities of these ionic species, as shown in Fig. 3(b).

The symmetric extension of alkyl chains does not always enhance solubilities across all solvents, a phenomenon related to activity coefficients. For instance, increasing the alkyl chain length decreases the aqueous solubility of dioxathogens [45]. A similar conclusion was observed when shifting from the ethyl group to the benzyl group in viologen derivatives. While the solubility of N,N' -diethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium diiodide $[C_2(Py)_2C_2]I_2$, also known as ethyl viologen iodide (EV-I), is 1.5 M in water, benzyl viologen iodide (BV-I) presented a solubility of 0.04 M [46].

An asymmetric rearrangement of alkyl chain lengths can significantly lower melting properties with minimal influence on the interaction between ROMs and the solvent. This trend is consistent across asymmetric modifications. For example, imidazolium-based ionic liquids showed a marked reduction in melting points with an asymmetric addition of a few carbon atoms to their alkyl chains, as observed in 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate $[C_nC_1Im][PF_6]$ [47], 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate $[C_nC_1Im][BF_4]$ [48], and 1-alkyl-3-methylpyridinium chloride $[C_nC_1Py]Cl$ [49]. Specifically, Fig. 4(a) highlights a consistent decrease in melting temperature (T_m) [49] and enthalpy of melting (ΔH_m) [50] as the N -alkyl side chain length of 3-methylpyridinium chloride $[C_nC_1Py]Cl$ increases, attributed to enhanced molecular asymmetry. It is important to acknowledge that beyond a certain length, the continuous elongation of alkyl chains might result in increased T_m and ΔH_m due to prevailing van der Waals interactions [47–49].

Howmik et al. [51] showed that the melting temperature (T_m) and enthalpy of melting (ΔH_m) of viologens could be decreased by extending the length of the alkyl chains attached to hexylbipyridinium bromides $[C_n(Py)_2C_6]Br_2$. This study kept the size of one alkyl chain constant at six carbons while changing the size of the other chain from 5 to 12 methylene groups. The results obtained showed a behavior similar to that previously described for ionic liquids, on which an inverse relationship between alkyl chain length and melting properties is observed, as shown in Fig. 4(a). Remarkably, the symmetric viologen $[C_6(Py)_2C_6]Br_2$, with six carbons on both sides ($n = 6$), exhibited the highest melting temperature among the derivatives, in agreement with Carnelley's rule [39].

Hu et al. [52] further illustrates how solubility enhancements in ROMs could be achieved through derivatization with alkyl chains of variable length. Asymmetrical viologens with varied alkyl chain lengths showed differing solubilities, underscoring that through the melting properties, ROMs' solubilities can be effectively increased. The authors reported that symmetric viologens with alkyl side chains containing 3 or 4 methylene groups (3,3 and 4,4) presented lower solubility than the asymmetric derivative containing one side chain of each length (3,4) (Fig. 4(b)). While 1,1'-bis-[3-sulfonatopropyl]-4,4'-bipyridinium $[(C_3SO_3)(Py)_2(C_3SO_3)]$ and 1,1'-bis-[4-sulfonatobutyl]-4,4'-bipyridinium $[(C_4SO_3)(Py)_2(C_4SO_3)]$ present aqueous solubilities of ~ 1.2 M and ~ 0.9 M, respectively; 1-[3-sulfonatopropyl]-1'-[4-sulfonatobutane]-4,4'-bipyridinium $[(C_3SO_3)(Py)_2(C_4SO_3)]$ reached nearly 1.7 M under the same conditions.

3.2. Asymmetry by functionalization

The goal of asymmetry by functionalization strategy is to reduce ROM's melting properties by inducing asymmetry in ROM's molecular structure via modification of ligands or functional groups. This approach has proven to be effective for a variety of ROMs, including ferrocenes [53], ferrocyanides [54], and viologens [52]. Specifically, the introduction of a methyl group on each cyclopentadienyl ring of ferrocene (Fig. 5) significantly lowers its melting temperature from ~ 446 K to ~ 312 K. The authors used this reduction to produce liquid ferrocene on battery application; however, it is worth noting that its solubility in ethylene carbonate (EC) and diethyl carbonate (DEC) was increased up to 3 M by adding 2 methyls. It also potentially enhanced reaction kinetics in some cases and achieving a notable increase in volumetric charge density to approximately 68 Ah/L, which may contribute to higher energy density depending on the potential of the opposing electrolyte [53].

Moreover, asymmetrical reconfiguration of 2,2'-bipyridine and cyanide ligands around iron cores (Fig. 5) has yielded ROMs with aqueous solubilities from 1.5 up to 4.2 times greater than those with symmetrical arrangements of identical ligands [54]. For instance, a symmetric Fe^{II} core complexed with six cyanide anions (CN^-) , $[Fe^{II}(CN)_6]^{4-}$, or three dicarboxylate bipyridine ligands $(DcbPy^{2-})$, $[Fe^{II}(DcbPy)_3]^{4-}$, presents aqueous solubility levels of 0.6 M and 0.76 M, respectively, when paired with potassium counter cations. However, complexes with one bipyridine and four cyanide ligands $[Fe^{II}(DcbPy)(CN)_4]^{4-}$ or two bipyridines and two cyanides $[Fe^{II}(DcbPy)_2(CN)_2]^{4-}$ (Fig. 5) form hybrid ROMs with

Fig. 3. Effect of symmetric growth of alkyl chains on (a) melting temperature [11] and (b) aqueous solubility at 318.15 K [11,43,44] of symmetric quaternary ammonium salts formed with chloride Cl^- and bromide Br^- anions.

Fig. 4. (a) Melting temperatures (open symbols) [49] and enthalpies of melting [50] (full symbols) of $[\text{C}_n\text{C}_1\text{Py}]\text{Cl}$ (black) and $[\text{C}_n(\text{Py})_2\text{C}_6]\text{Br}_2$ (red) [51]; (b) solubilities of sulfonated bipyridinium derivatives $[(\text{C}_n\text{SO}_3)(\text{Py})_2(\text{C}_m\text{SO}_3)]$ [52] in water. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Molecular structure of ferrocenes and ferrocyanide derivatives, adapted from the literature [54].

enhanced aqueous solubilities of 1.22 M or 1.12 M, respectively [54].

Differently from the asymmetry by alkylation strategy, functionalization may result in a robust modification of ROMs' molecular structure. For instance, the replacement of two ferrocyanide ligands (CN) with DcbPy would promote the exposure of carboxylate radicals, which could produce different intermolecular interactions with other ROMs. This change should result in different lattice energies, therefore, different enthalpies of melting ΔH_m . The asymmetry of alkylation also promotes such modifications, however, to a lesser magnitude since the same functional groups are present in ROMs' structure. Therefore, the asymmetry by functionalization should induce a reduction of T_m by hindering the formation of a crystal lattice (an entropic effect explained by Carnelley's rule), but it should also promote significant changes in ΔH_m due to the formation of different intermolecular interactions. This effect implies that the asymmetry by functionalization could result in significant changes in solubility; however, it is also associated with a higher risk related to the unwanted increase of ΔH_m .

Differently from the asymmetry by alkylation strategy, the functionalization may result in a robust modification on ROMs' molecular structure. For instance, the replacement of two ferrocyanide ligands (CN) over the DcbPy would promote the exposure of carboxylate radicals which could produce different intermolecular interactions with other ROMs. This change should result in different lattice energies, therefore, different enthalpies of melting ΔH_m . The asymmetry of alkylation also promote such modifications, however, at a minor magnitude since the same functional groups are present in ROMs' structure. Therefore, the asymmetry by functionalization should induce reduction of T_m by diffculting the formation of chrystal lattice (entropic effect explained by Carnelley's rule), but also should promote significant changes on the ΔH_m due to the formation of different intermolecular interactions. This effect implicates that the asymmetry by functionalization could result in high changes on solubilities, however it is also associated with a higher risk related to the unwanted increase of ΔH_m .

3.3. Asymmetry by substitution pattern

Adjusting the structural symmetry by rearranging the insertion sites of functional groups on ROMs is a poorly explored strategy that could significantly modulate their melting temperatures and enhance solubilities. For instance, while 1,4-dimethylbenzene, with two symmetrical axes, melts at 286.15 K its 1,2- or 1,3-disubstituted positional isomers exhibit significantly lower melting points of 248.15 K and 226.15 K, respectively [55] (Fig. 6). The effectiveness of this approach extends beyond benzene to include derivatives with various functional groups like fluorine, chlorine, bromine, iodine, and nitrogen, underscoring broad applicability across different ROMs [40].

Mao et al. [56] applied this approach to increase the aqueous solubilities of disulfonated anthraquinones [AQDS] by adjusting the sulfonation positions (Fig. 7). The results obtained showed that shifting sulfonate positions from 1,5- to 2,7-, increases solubility between 6 and 38 times, depending on the counter cation of the anthraquinone. For example, [Mg][1,5-AQDS] and [Mg][2,7-AQDS] presented aqueous solubilities of 0.0838 M and 1.26 M, respectively. Similar behaviors were observed by rearranging functional groups of other quinone redox-active derivatives [56].

Nevertheless, the rearrangement of methyl group from symmetrical [4- C_1 HPy] $^+$ to asymmetrical [3- C_1 HPy] $^+$ (Fig. 6) increased both melting temperature and enthalpy of the corresponding salt [3- C_1 HPy][CH_3SO_3], instead of reducing it [57]. This report suggests that the substitution pattern on charged species may present additional effects beyond the asymmetry as predicted by Carnelley's rule [39].

3.4. Effect of asymmetry strategies on activity coefficients

Enhancing the solubility of ROMs by reducing their melting properties requires careful attention to changes in activity coefficients. Although some organic solutes show a direct correlation between melting properties and solubility, this relationship often does not hold for ionic species [58]. It is crucial to ensure that strategies for lowering melting points do not result in significant shifts in activity coefficients. Such changes could negate the solubility benefits achieved by reducing melting properties. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate whether the methods used to lower melting points also result in increased activity coefficients, as this would counteract the intended improvement in solubility. All activity coefficients estimated within this section were predicted by COSMO-RS considering infinite dilution of the solute.

3.4.1. Asymmetry by alkylation

Elongation of alkyl chains can decrease the melting temperatures of charged species, as shown earlier. However, a reduced melting tem-

perature does not always lead to increased solubility. Foster et al. [59] examined the influence of alkyl chain length on the melting temperature and solubility of alkyl *p*-hydroxybenzoates in water and hexane. An increase in alkyl chain length lowered melting properties as expected, but this strategy only increased solubilities in hexane, not in water (Fig. 8 (a)). This discrepancy arises because solubility is governed by a trade-off between melting properties and the activity coefficients (γ).

Although increasing the alkyl chain decreased γ in hexane, it exponentially increased its value in water (Fig. 8(b)), indicating that non-favorable interactions with water arise from the increase in alkyl chain length, negating the effect of melting temperature depression. In other words, as expected, increasing the apolar volume of a ROM aiming at decreasing its melting properties, inevitably leads to weaker interactions with water or aqueous-based solvents. The trade-off between these two consequences defines whether the aqueous solubility of a ROM is enhanced or decreased.

An asymmetric increase in alkyl chain length effectively reduces melting properties. However, it may require the addition of excessive methylene groups to achieve significant reductions. If dissolved in highly polar solvents, such as water or ethanol, ROM solubility may actually decrease due to increasing activity coefficients, akin to what was observed in the previous section for alkyl *p*-hydroxybenzoates. Manipulating the length of alkyl chains through asymmetric arrangements reduces melting properties with minimal changes to the size of functional groups, likely exerting little impact on activity coefficients across various solvents. Xu et al. [42] explored the effect of asymmetric alkylation pattern on quaternary ammonium salts concerning their melting temperatures, activity coefficients, and solubility in ethylene and dimethyl carbonates (EC/DMC = 1:1). Fig. 9(a) illustrates that the deletion of a single $-CH_2-$ group from symmetric tetraethylammonium salts ([N_{2222}][R] vs [N_{2221}][R]) leads to a significant decrease in melting temperature with only minor changes in activity coefficients. The minor modification on the sigma profile is associated with small changes on charge density distribution of [N_{2222}] $^+$ and [N_{2221}] $^+$, as it can be seen by the similar colors of its induced charge density distribution (Fig. 9(b)) and sigma profiles (Figs. 9(b) and S3). Since the strategy of asymmetry by alkylation promoted reduction of melting property without any compromise on activity coefficient, the change from [N_{2222}] $^+$ to [N_{2221}] $^+$ effectively increased its solubility, regardless of the counterion involved. Although not tested, this strategy could also have resulted in positive results if applied on other solvents and charged or discharged species.

Sigma profiles are graphical representations that illustrate the distribution of surface charge density on molecules, providing insights into their polarity and interaction sites. By plotting molecular surface area against charge density (σ), sigma profiles highlight regions of positive

Fig. 6. Molecular structure and symmetric axis (blue lines) of 1,2-, dimethylbenzene, and 2-, 3- and 4-methylpyridinium cation. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Molecular structures of 2,7- and 1,5-disulfonated anthraquinones.

Fig. 9. Comparison of (a) melting temperature (empty symbols) and activity coefficients (filled symbols); and (b) solubilities in the EC/DMC solvent system (normal conditions) of salts formed with triethylmethylammonium [N2221] (blue) and tetraethylammonium [N2222] (red) cations, coupled with trifluoromethanesulfonate [CF₃SO₃], hexafluorophosphate [PF₆], tetrafluoroborate [BF₄], and hexafluoroarsenate [AsF₆] anions [42]. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

and negative charge, with peaks indicating areas of higher charge density that influence solubility, reactivity, and other properties. Understanding sigma profiles enables researchers to predict how structural changes can affect the behavior of a molecule in different environments.

As shown in Fig. 10(b), the sigma profiles of [(C₃SO₃)(Py)₂(C₄SO₃)], [(C₄SO₃)(Py)₂(C₄SO₃)] and [(C₃SO₃)(Py)₂(C₄SO₃)] are quite similar, with the primary difference around $-0.004 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^2$, attributed to the incremental contribution of methylene groups (-CH₂-). The [(C₄SO₃)(Py)₂(C₄SO₃)] exhibits the highest peak due to a higher amount of methylene groups linking the sulfonate to the pyridinium groups. These

marginal contributions of -CH₂- result in minor changes in charge density distribution, causing minimal alterations in activity coefficients (Fig. 10(a)). Hu et al. [52] recognized that asymmetry by alkylation could increase the solubility of viologen derivatives by reducing their melting properties. However, their success was primarily because the management of methylene groups did not significantly increase the activity coefficient.

3.4.2. Asymmetry by substitution pattern

Fig. 11(a) illustrates the activity coefficients and sigma profiles of

Fig. 10. (a) Aqueous solubility [52] and activity coefficient at room temperature and (b) sigma profiles of viologen derivatives: $[(C_3SO_3)(Py)_2(C_3SO_3)]$ (red), $[(C_3SO_3)(Py)_2(C_4SO_3)]$ (green), and $[(C_4SO_3)(Py)_2(C_4SO_3)]$ (blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. Activity coefficient and sigma profiles of (a) dimethylbenzene isomers in EC/DMC (1:1) and water, and (b) disulfonated anthraquinones and their solubility in water [56].

dimethylbenzene isomers, differing in substitution pattern. The similarity in sigma profiles indicates that these isomers would promote similar interactions with the solvent. It was verified by their close activity coefficients regardless of the solvent, water or EC/DMC. Since the strategy of changing substitution pattern to promote asymmetry (Fig. 6) simultaneously reduced melting properties [55] and did not change their activity coefficients, this strategy was successfully able to increase dimethylbenzene solubilities, regardless of the solvent used.

Fig. 11(b) demonstrates that when a substitution pattern strategy is applied to anthraquinones charged species, significant modifications were observed on both sigma profile and activity coefficients. In silico analysis of anthraquinone derivatives indicates that the change of substitution pattern changed the distance between two of the most highly charged spots of these ROMs, of sulfonium and oxygen groups. While the position 1,5- brings $[-SO_3]$ and $[=O]$ closer, 2,7- keep them apart. The closer these groups are, their charge densities are more dispersed.

This effect can be visualized on Fig. 11(b) 2-D image of anthraquinone charge distribution and on their sigma profiles (Fig. S2).

The comparison of results between the activity coefficient of dimethylbenzene and anthraquinone cases evidence that the strategy of substitution pattern requires careful attention when the central core of the ROM has sites with localized charges, such as the anthraquinone's oxygen. In such cases, the modification of substitution insertion position would not just change asymmetry, but also the activity coefficient.

The substitution pattern strategy can be an effective tool for reducing melting temperature and increase solubility especially for ROMs with dispersed charges. Those that contain punctual charges would also require further evaluation of activity coefficients.

3.4.3. Asymmetry by functionalization

This section focuses on evaluating changes in the activity coefficient when promoting asymmetry by introducing new ligands or functional

groups on ROMs. Fig. 12 reveals that the activity coefficients of ferrocyanide derivatives, analyzed by Li et al. [54], significantly influence their water solubilities. Previous studies [60] inaccurately attributed the enhanced solubilities of certain ferrocyanide derivatives, such as $K_4[Fe^{II}(CN)_4(DcbPy)]$ and $K_4[Fe^{II}(CN)_2(DcbPy)_2]$, solely to their asymmetric configuration. However, the broad range of activity coefficients and the lack of a direct correlation of the melting properties with water solubility suggest that while melting temperatures and enthalpies play an important role in the solubility of these ROMs, they do not fully explain the behavior observed. When modifying/adding ligands or functional groups, targeting asymmetry alone should not be the focus of ROMs' structural optimization.

Substitution pattern and modification of functional groups promoted substantial variations in melting properties and activity coefficients. Likely also presenting an influence on electrochemical performance and possibly promoting unwanted side reactions. Thus, these strategies are recommended for the development of disruptive and innovative systems, whose properties and performances would have to be further studied.

3.5. Considerations and applicability

Reducing the melting properties of redox-active organic molecules (ROMs) offers a promising approach to enhance their solubility in electrolyte solutions, thereby potentially increasing the energy density of redox flow batteries (RFBs). However, the impact of these strategies on activity coefficients must be carefully evaluated, as even slight increases in activity coefficients could offset solubility gains achieved through reduced melting points.

The COSMO-RS predictions indicate that the strategies of alkylation with minimal carbon modifications and substitution pattern on non-charged ROMs can reduce melting properties without major modification on the activity coefficients, regardless of the solvent. Since these strategies are primarily entropically driven (via hindered formation of a crystal lattice), their application could yield improvements with only minor structural changes compared to enthalpically driven modification. However, since only minor modification in charge density distributions were observed, the application of these strategies should increase solubility regardless of the supporting electrolyte. If applicable, these strategies are recommended for systems which already present at least moderate ROM solubilities.

Especially the asymmetry by alkylation strategy with minor modification on carbon numbers may be effectively applied to increase the solubility of ROMs at different charging states, addressing issues of solid

precipitation upon charge/discharge and low energy density of virtually all RFB systems. Thus, this strategy could be applied.

Strategies of Asymmetry induction through ligand modifications or changes in substitution patterns should reduce melting properties; however, they may also be associated with changes in activity coefficients. If these strategies reduce activity coefficients, a major solubility increase could be achieved. Conversely, an unfavorable change may offset or even negate the benefits of reduced melting properties. Predictive tools, such as COSMO-RS, are essential for evaluating the activity coefficient in conjunction with melting property modifications to anticipate overall solubility effects accurately. This strategy is recommended for high risk high gain approaches, aimed at disruptive discoveries, or when a robust increase in solubility is essential to increase energy density. Additional considerations can be found in Table 1.

4. Activity coefficients

This section presents three thermodynamic strategies to increase the solubility of redox-active organic molecules in electrolytes by targeting the reduction of their activity coefficients. As this parameter governs molecular interactions, these approaches aim to promote more favorable solute-solvent interactions. The first strategy involves modifying molecular structures to reduce activity coefficients (Molecular Structure Modifications). The second focuses on adding ions or changing counterions to lower γ (Ions Selection). The third strategy employs solvent mixtures or co-solvents to enhance interactions, thereby increasing ROM solubility (Mixed Solvents).

4.1. Molecular structure modifications

Modifying the functional groups or ligands of redox-active molecules can promote a more efficient increase in ROM solubility if these modifications are targeted at reducing activity coefficients. Carrington et al. [61] demonstrated that functional group modifications significantly impact the solubilities of bipyridinium salts, with variations ranging from 0.5 M to 3.2 M across derivatives containing 20 different functional groups. While the aqueous solubility of neutral ferrocene is approximately 10 μ M [62], derivatives with polar radicals, including a quaternary ammonium moiety and chloride counterions, exhibited solubility up to 1.9 M [33]. These examples demonstrate that substantial increases in solubilities can be achieved by strategically shifting functional groups or ligands of ROMs.

The addition of functional groups such as sulfonate, phosphonate, carboxylate, quaternary ammonium ($-NR_3^+$), and hydroxyl groups were previously recommended to increase the aqueous solubilities of ROMs [3,4,63]. Some of these studies attribute the enhancements in aqueous solubility to the introduction of electrostatic repulsion by sulfonate and phosphonate groups, which prevents excessive aggregation. Carboxylate groups help stabilize the molecule through electrostatic interactions, particularly in alkaline pH. Quaternary ammoniums provide electronic isolation and can prevent dimerization or excessive aggregation. Hydrophilic groups such as hydroxyl and amino improve interaction with water by forming hydrogen bonds, reducing the activity coefficient and aiding the stabilization of radical intermediates [5,64]. Although useful, these heuristic recommendations do not provide an in-depth understanding of the interactions or guidelines about insertion positions and alkyl chain lengths of functional groups.

The prediction of activity coefficients can provide valuable insights when complex structural modifications are required. For instance, bis(3-trimethylammonium)propyl viologen ($[BTMAP-V]Cl_4$) presented high solubility and stability, although associated with a high cost of synthesis. Lv et al. [32] identified that a similar quaternary ammonium viologen derivative with two additional hydroxyl groups could be synthesized via a simpler and cheaper route from a common and inexpensive industrial chemical, 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropyl trimethylammonium chloride

Fig. 12. Activity coefficient and water solubility [54] of potassium Fe^{II} derivatives with cyanide (CN^-) and dicarboxylate bipyridine ($DcbPy^{2-}$) ligands.

Table 1
Analysis of melting properties strategies to enhance ROM solubility.

Strategy	Main advantages	Disadvantages	Considerations
Asymmetry by Alkylation (Section 2.1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimal impact on activity coefficients (γ) - Broad solvent compatibility - Requires only minor structural changes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long alkyl chains may increase γ in polar solvents - Less effective than enthalpic modifications - Synthesis may be complex 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Best for ROMs with modifiable alkyl chains - Estimate γ in polar solvents - Suitable for minor solubility increase ($<10\times^*$)
Asymmetry by Functionalization (Section 2.2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can strongly enhance solubility via ΔH_m reduction - Versatile due to several functionalization options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May cause electrochemical interference or side reactions - Requires γ evaluation - Difficult screening since ΔH_m effects are hard to predict 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use for major solubility increase ($>10\times^*$) - High-risk, high-reward strategy, recommended for disruptive discoveries. - Must assess electrochemistry and γ.
Asymmetry by Substitution Pattern (Section 2.3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Broad solvent compatibility, especially for non-charged ROMs - No functional group addition/removal needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May increase γ in ROMs with localized charges - Potential electrochemical changes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ideal for aromatic ROMs with multiple functional groups - Evaluate γ via COSMO-RS - Suited for minor solubility increase ($<10\times^*$)

* The $10\times$ solubility increase benchmark is a heuristic estimate based on solute solubility comparisons, distinguishing minor from major enhancements.

(commonly known as dextrosil). Therefore, forming the bis(3-trimethylammonio-2-hydroxy)propyl viologen tetrachloride [Dex-V]Cl₄. The authors presumed that the addition of hydroxyl groups would further increase the solubility of this species by promoting additional hydrogen bonds with water. However, the experimental aqueous solubility of these derivatives was found to be equivalent, around 2.0 M. Other studies have also reported that introducing hydrophilic groups can significantly increase solubility, but excessive hydrogen bonding can restrict these gains [58]. Lv et al. [32] attributed the lack of solubility increase to the challenging organization of water molecules around the hydroxyl group, though they did not present experimental or theoretical evidence for this hypothesis.

Fig. 13 presents the induced charge distribution profile of both viologen derivatives, [BTMAP-V]Cl₄ and [Dex-V]Cl₄. In silico evaluation indicates that the position of the -OH groups inserted indeed created a highly positive charge around the hydroxyl group, as shown by the violet colour of [Dex-V]Cl₄ in Fig. 13(a). However, when interacting with the chloride anions, the charges contributed to the dispersion of the negative charge density distribution of chlorides, as observed by the reduction of [Dex-V]Cl₄ peak around 0.018 e/Å² (Fig. 13(b)). This promoted an increase in the activity coefficient of [BTMAP-V]Cl₄ from -4.58 to -0.72 for [Dex-V]Cl₄ (Table 2). Of course, this discussion ignores expected severe changes in the melting properties of these two compounds, and assumes accurate activity coefficient predictions from COSMO-RS using ion-pair conformations that despite being particularly stable under the DFT configuration used are different across the two compounds. Nevertheless, the goal of this example is to reinforce that although heuristic guidelines [3,4,63] can provide valuable information, they must be taken as general rules, especially when complex

interactions and structural modifications involve inherent trade-offs.

In addition to the position of the functional group, COSMO-RS can be a powerful tool for evaluating the size of the alkyl chain attached to the ROM core. For instance, Liu et al. [66] studied the influence of alkyl chain length on hydroxyalkyl viologen derivatives. They measured the experimental aqueous solubility of derivatives containing alkyl chains with 2, 3, and 6 carbons (Table 2, and Fig. 14). The experimental solubilities indicate that all derivatives have high solubility in water, consistent with the negative values of activity coefficients. Following conventional guidelines, the reader might expect that adding non-polar methylene groups (-CH₂-) could hinder interaction with water and increase the activity coefficient. However, as shown by experimental solubility, the increase from 2 to 3 carbons on the alkyl chain actually increased the solubility. Liu et al. [66] also tested a derivative with a 6-carbon alkyl chain, which presented lower aqueous solubility. Without using activity coefficient models for their interpretation, the authors could not explain why the increase from 2 to 3 methylene groups resulted in an increase of solubility.

Fig. 14 shows a comparison of the activity coefficients (COSMO-RS) of hydroxyalkyl viologen derivatives with alkyl chains of varying lengths (from $n = 1$ to $n = 6$, [C_nOH-V]Cl₂). The minimum activity coefficients were reached around 4 and 5 carbons, showing that in these cases an increase in chain length may actually, and counterintuitively, lead to enhanced solubilities. Furthermore, in silico evaluation of charge density distributions (Fig. S1) indicates that reducing the alkyl carbon chain from 3 to 2 or 1 tends to bring the hydroxyl radicals closer to the chloride anions attracted to the positive core of pyridinium. This interaction may disperse its punctual charge and actually increase the activity coefficient. This effect becomes negligible when alkyl chains are

Fig. 13. Charge density distribution and sigma profile of (a) charged and (b) neutral viologen derivatives.

Table 2
Activity coefficient and solubility of viologen derivatives in water at room conditions.

Viologen derivative	Molecular structure	Activity coeff. Ln (γ)	Solubility [M]	Ref.
[M-V]Cl ₂ (1910-42-5)		-3.56	3.0	[65]
[BTMAP-V]Cl ₄		-4.58	2.0	[33]
[Dex-V]Cl ₄		-0.72	2.0	[32]
[C ₃ OH-V]Cl ₂		-5.47	2.69	[34]
[C ₂ OH-V]Cl ₂		-3.08	1.87	[34]
[C ₆ OH-V]Cl ₂		-5.86	1.82	[34]

Fig. 14. COSMO-RS Activity coefficient and experimental water solubility [66] of hydroxyalkyl viologens ($V-[(CH_2)_n-OH]_2^{2+}$) with alkyl chain length varying from $n = 1$ to 6.

longer than 3 carbons, justifying why derivatives with 4 and 5 presented the lowest activity coefficient. However, long alkyl chains increase the non-polar surface of the compound, thereby reducing the affinity between viologen and water and increasing the activity coefficient. This in silico analysis indicates that a minimum activity coefficient is achieved between 3 and 5 carbons, as shown in Fig. 14.

Additionally, if the strategy of asymmetry by alkylation pattern were applied, a further solubility increase could be expected for these hydroxyalkyl viologen derivatives. For instance, 1-hydroxybutyl-1'-hydroxypentyl-4,4'-bipyridinium dichloride ($[C_{4,5}-OH-V]Cl_2$) could theoretically present higher solubilities than all derivatives studied by Liu et al. [66] due to its lower activity coefficient and melting properties. This example shows how the utilization of COSMO-RS can be an effective tool to screen for ROM derivatives with higher solubilities.

4.2. Ions selection

The solubilities of charged ROMs are influenced by the presence of ions in the electrolyte solution. These ions may be the counterions of

ROMs or may come from an external salt. As counterions, these species exert a significant influence on intermolecular interactions, thereby modifying both the melting properties and activity coefficients of ROMs, as demonstrated, for example, by Vilas-Boas et al. [11]. Note, though, that when the ions are from an external salt, and considering no ion exchange issues upon ROM crystallization, they influence the electrolyte solution and not melting properties, affecting solvent-solvent and solvent-solute interactions such as their hydration shell and overall solvation dynamics [67]. Understanding these interactions and identifying trends is crucial for the optimal management of ions in solution to increase ROM solubility.

4.2.1. Counterions

Selecting the appropriate counterions for ROMs can be challenging, particularly in battery applications. Even if neutral ROMs do not require counterions, such as sulfonated viologen zwitterions [52], these species will need counterions after charging/discharging redox reactions, to balance the charge formed by the electron migration. The management of these ions should aim at forming weak lattice structures and ensuring optimal interaction with the solvent (low activity coefficient).

David et al. [58] studied the effect of counterions on the aqueous solubility of organic species. They concluded that smaller, compact counterions increase aqueous solubilities compared to larger ones. Larger ions tend to disperse their charges, which contribute to the reduction of melting properties but decrease solvation energies, thereby increasing the activity coefficient. Overall, for organic species that contain ionic interactions, the solvation energies seem to have a more significant impact than the reduction of melting properties. Additionally, adding hydrophilic groups to the counter-ion can enhance solubility, but beyond a certain point, excessive hydrogen bonding can decrease it. This study also reported that a significant part of the counterions' influence on aqueous solubility is related to their impact on local pH [58]. By controlling pH to 6.0, counterions' influence was significantly reduced.

COSMO-RS predictions for the aqueous solubility of 1500 ionic liquids (ILs), comprising 50 cations and 30 anions showed that anions have a greater influence than cations on shifting activity coefficients [20]. As a general trend, COSMO-RS predictions indicate that small anions, such as chloride, or anions containing hydrophilic groups, namely acetate, phosphonate, and sulfonate groups, lead to increased aqueous solubilities. Cations containing highly hydrophilic functional groups, such as hydroxyl, amine, or sulfonate, also contribute to the increase of IL aqueous solubilities. Overall, counter-anions presented greater influence than counter-cations on aqueous solubility [20]. Tomé et al. [68] attributed this effect to anions being more polarizable and strongly hydrated than cations, which leads to more pronounced interactions with water.

While the anions exert a major influence, the cations may also play a role in the solubility of ROMs. Mao et al. [56] showed that the solubility of anthraquinones varies with different cations, following the order $[Mg]^{2+} > [Na]^+ > [K]^+ > [Ca]^{2+} > [Ba]^{2+}$. Carretero-González et al. [69] studied the solubility of sulfonated quinzarin and alizarin derivatives formed with different counter-cations. The influence of the cation depended on the derivative studied, but the overall tendency followed the order: $[P(CH_2OH)_4]^+ > [N(C_2H_4OH)_4]^+ > [Na]^+$.

Converting ROMs into ionic liquids is also a possible alternative to increase their solubility. Aldous et al. [70] synthesized two ferrocene derivatives by incorporating its structure into the cation or anion of $[C_2C_1im][NTf_2]$. By tethering ferrocene (Fc) to either the anion or the cation, giving the corresponding ferrocenylsulfonate(trifluoromethylsulfonate)imide anion ($[FcNTf]^-$) or the 1-ethyl-3-(methylferrocenyl)imidazolium cation ($[C_2C_1imFc]^+$), the solubility of these ROM derivatives increased in $[C_2C_1im][NTf_2]$. The Fc incorporation in the anion resulted in the highest increase, reaching up to 125 mmol/kg for $[C_2C_1im][FcNTf]$, far exceeding that of unmodified ferrocene. COSMO-RS predictions of activity coefficients indicate that the

incorporation of ferrocene into the anion promoted a mild reduction of the activity coefficient from 1.88 to 1.21. Although the melting properties of this ferrocene derivative are unknown, large organic ionic structures such as this are known for promoting reduced melting points [71]. Therefore, the incorporation of ferrocene into the IL anion reduced the activity coefficient and presumably decreased the melting temperature, consequently increasing the solubility of this ROM derivative, as experimentally proven.

4.2.2. Salting-in and salting-out

The addition of salts into aqueous solutions induces a variety of novel interactions. Often, it reduces the aqueous solubilities of existing solutes, an effect known as salting-out. In fewer cases the contrary occurs, and the salt addition increases the solubility of the existing solutes, a phenomenon known as salting-in. The molecular level mechanism by which ions operate in aqueous solutions remains not fully understood. One of the most accepted theories correlated salting-in and salting-out effects to the balance of two types of interactions: (i) the formation of hydration complexes around the ions, and (ii) the interaction between ions and the hydrophobic moiety of the solute [68,72].

Interaction (i) is related to the competition of the ions of the added salt for water, fostering ion-water interactions in detriment of those between water and ROMs. This leads to the salting-out effect, with its intensity positively correlating with the interaction strength between water molecules and the ions of the added salt. Interaction (ii) increases solubility due to the aggregation of added ions around hydrophobic moieties of ROMs. This typically occurs through the hydrophobic effect, where less polar moieties of ions and solute are forced together, shielding themselves from the solvent and maximizing water-water hydrogen bonding [73]. Ions with dispersed charges usually favor these interactions due to their lower solvation energy and, thus, lower water-ion interaction energies. Salting-in occurs when interaction (ii) predominates over interaction (i), while salting-out predominates when interaction (i) is stronger. Managing the salts in solution to increase salting-in or reduce salting-out can enhance ROM solubility in an electrolyte solution.

For example, the addition of MgSO_4 and NaSCN to an electrolyte solution can be used as a theoretical exercise. Mg^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} are ions with highly concentrated charges, as indicated by their colour (violet and red) and sigma profiles ($-0.06 \text{ e}/\text{Å}^2$ and $0.023 \text{ e}/\text{Å}^2$, respectively in Fig. 15). Both ions have a high concentration of charges, which would more likely interact with water molecules (i) and have a low probability of interacting with hydrophobic non-polar regions of the solute (ii). Thus, the addition of MgSO_4 would predominantly promote salting out. Although Na^+ also has a highly concentrated charge, its charge is much lower than Mg^{2+} , which would at least reduce the stability of the complex formed with water (i) and decrease the salting-out effect. If

Fig. 15. Charge density distribution of Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , SO_4^{2-} , and SCN^- obtained by COSMO-RS.

possible, one could consider replacing Mg^{2+} with 2 Na^+ to reduce the salting-out effect and, therefore, increase the solubility of ROMs in this electrolyte solution. The SCN^- anion has low and dispersed charges, which should contribute to effect (ii), while forming less stable complexes with water (lower effect (i)). The addition of SCN^- into the system would have a higher probability of promoting salting-in of ROMs.

Although most salts are known to induce salting-out, i.e. decrease the solubility of a solute by decreasing the amount of free water available, the ions at the extreme of the Hofmeister series [74,75] (Fig. 16), commonly known by the obsolete designation of chaotropes, may actually induce an increase in solubility (salting-in). This series was developed to study the effects of salts on protein solubilization, but previous studies have shown that this series can also be extended to other systems, such as polymers [76], ionic liquids [77], and thus, ROM solubilities in aqueous solutions. While ions with high charge density, such as CO_3^{2-} and Ba^{2+} , are more likely to promote salting-out, ions with more dispersed charges, such as SCN^- and $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_4^+$, are likely to promote salting-in. The reader can use this series (Fig. 16) to identify salt additives that would enhance the solubility of ROMs for specific electrochemical applications.

This empirical ranking is particularly useful for selecting the appropriate ions to achieve desired solubility behaviors without the need for extensive computational resources. Previous studies [68,72,75] identified that the anions have a more impactful effect on the solute solubility than the cations, and that the pH does not significantly influence salting-in or -out effects. Thus, it is possible to identify that cations like quaternary ammonium, or anions such as thiocyanate, nitrate, or perchlorate, may induce a salting-in effect and increase solubility that may be used to advantage in the formulation of electrolytes to be used in redox flow batteries. Freire et al. [72,77] and Tomé et al. [68] demonstrated how nitrate, thiocyanate, and perchlorate anions, unlike sulfate or chlorate, can enhance the solubility of hydrophobic imidazolium-based ionic liquids in an aqueous solution. As for the salting-in mechanism, Freire et al. [72], using NMR and MD, established that “the controlling interactions that determine the salting-in phenomena in large charged molecules take place between the salt ions and the hydrophobic moiety of the solute”. Tomé et al. [68] in a follow-up work showed the same effect for amino acids, which are zwitterions and thus relevant for understanding, by analogy, the behavior of some ROMs that also are zwitterions. In addition to adding salting-in salts, reducing the concentration of ions that promote salting-out may be a powerful tool to increase the solubility of a preexisting functional system. For instance, by reducing the concentration of sulfate or carbonate anions or Mg^{2+} or Ca^{2+} cations.

Besides controlling the solubility, the choice of ions in electrolytic solutions can also affect the stability of ROMs. A previous review [5] reported that lithium ions (Li^+) are often used to stabilize higher oxidation states of ROMs in redox flow battery solutions due to their ability to interact favorably with various molecular structures. Anions like bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (NTf_2^-) are used to stabilize ROMs in non-aqueous solutions because of their low nucleophilicity and good solvation capacity, which reduce undesired reactivity. Complexation with cations such as zinc (Zn^{2+}) and magnesium (Mg^{2+}) can also stabilize charged forms of ROMs and enhance solubility. These ionic interactions are crucial for optimizing the performance and stability of ROMs in different electrolytic environments.

4.3. Mixed solvents

The solubility of redox-active organic molecules (ROMs) can be significantly enhanced by introducing co-solvents, which modify the solvent environment and affect interactions between solvent and solute molecules. Singh and Byon [5] presented several experimental examples of effectively using mixed solvents to increase the solubility of ROMs. For instance, acetic acid increased methylene blue solubility from 0.6 M to 1.8 M in H_2SO_4 solutions, and hexadecyltrimethylammonium

Fig. 16. Ions influence on salting-in and salting-out according to the Hofmeister series.

chloride increased TEMPO's aqueous solubility from 0.08 M to 0.8 M. Note that there exists a large overlap between the salting-in effect discussed in the previous section and the general theme of co-solvency. In a way, some of the salts discussed for their salting-in effect can already be considered co-solvents, although the topic of co-solvency usually revolves around organic liquids and hydrotropes. For example, Dong et al. [78] experimentally evaluated several additives to increase and stabilize zinc acetate solutions for redox flow battery applications. They identified that potassium acetate (salt), urea (organic molecule), and acetamide (organic molecule) are effective in constructing highly concentrated zinc acetate electrolytes.

The Scatchard-Hildebrand theory [79] provides a fundamental approach for understanding how co-solvents influence solubility, positing that solubility is maximized when the solubility parameter of the solvent mixture aligns closely with that of the solute. This concept aligns with the 'like dissolves like' principle, where solvent polarity plays a critical role. Specifically, solubility is enhanced when the polarities of the solute and solvent mixture are similar, as this facilitates effective molecular interactions. For example, polar solutes, such as certain ROMs, dissolve more readily in polar solvents like water or acetonitrile, while non-polar solutes favor solvents like hexane. In mixed solvent systems, adding a co-solvent adjusts the overall polarity of the mixture, tailoring it to the solute's characteristics to optimize solubility. This polarity-dependent effect is evident in practical applications, such as the increased solubility of methylene blue in H_2SO_4 with acetic acid as a co-solvent, as reported by Singh and Byon [5].

Although the Scatchard-Hildebrand theory presents a straightforward understanding, it may not be accurate for complex mixtures. The mixed solvent strategy can be guided by the permittivity or dielectric constant of the solvent. Specifically, in organic solvents, the relative permittivity, a measure of the ability of a solvent to reduce the electrostatic interactions between charged particles, plays a pivotal role in this enhancement [80]. Higher dielectric constants weaken the Coulombic attraction between ions, facilitating greater dissociation of electrolytes and improving the solubility of redox-active species.

Therefore, higher relative permittivity, especially in organic solvents, should lead to higher solubility of ROMs. Solvents such as acetonitrile (AN), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), propylene carbonate (PC), 1,2-butylene carbonate (BC), and γ -valerolactone (GVL) could be efficient co-solvents due to their high dielectric constants, especially for organic solvents [80].

Wang et al. [81] found that the addition of the co-solvents diethyl carbonate (DEC), dimethylformamide (DMF), 1,3-dioxolane (DOL), or dimethyl carbonate (DMC) to acetonitrile (AN) increased 1,4-di-tert-butyl-2,5-dimethoxybenzene (DBB) solubility. However, the addition of the same co-solvents reduced the solubility of benzophenone (BP) in AN. This study demonstrates that selecting an appropriate combination of solvent and co-solvents for each ROM is crucial for each ROM-electrolyte system.

Fig. 17 presents the COSMO-RS activity coefficient of neutral DBB on AC solutions containing several co-solvents at 298.15 K, and at a 9:1 proportion of AC:co-solvent. The four co-solvents studied by Wang et al. [81] were considered (blue bars), alongside to other 31 materials used as solvent on battery applications. COSMO-RS predicted that the co-solvents increase DBB solubility in AC (red bar) follow the order: DEC > DMC > DOL > DMF, which is the same order found in experiments (blue bars) [81]. The prediction of the utilization of other co-solvents shown in Fig. 17 indicate that even higher theoretical energy densities of DBB batteries could have been achieved if other co-solvents were used, such as toluene, heptanol, gamma-decalactone, or 4,4-dibutyl-gamma-butyrolactone. Gamma-butyrolactone, for instance, presents higher relative permittivity than acetonitrile [80], indicating that the solubility of charged DBB could also be increase.

These examples indicate that COSMO-RS can be used as an effective predictive tool to evaluate several strategies to increase the solubility of ROMs. However, ensuring that the solubility of charged ROMs is also increased or, at least, maintained is also crucial for the effective operation of the battery. Furthermore, the application of the presented thermodynamic strategies may also promote modifications in the electrochemical stability and performance of the batteries, which must be

Fig. 17. COSMO-RS activity coefficient at 298.15 K of 1,4-di-tert-butyl-2,5-dimethoxybenzene (DBB) in acetonitrile with different co-solvents at 9:1 proportion.

considered. By integrating these strategies and focusing on the underlying thermodynamic principles, researchers and engineers can significantly improve ROMs' solubility and energy density of RFB. A strategic increase in solubility should also reduce the risk of unwanted precipitation, and allow the use of a wider variety of ROMs on RFB.

As stated at the beginning of this section, co-solvency is an umbrella term for several solubilization mechanisms. The last of which discussed in this section is hydrotropy. The aqueous solubility of hydrophobic solutes, including ROMs, can be enhanced by adding an amphiphilic molecule (i.e., hydrotrope) to the mixture [82]. Driven by the hydrophobic effect, the apolar moieties of this hydrotrope aggregate around those of the hydrophobic solute, shielding it from water and preventing its crystallization. On the other hand, the polar moieties of the hydrotrope maintain favorable interactions with water, making hydrotropes highly soluble molecules. Note the similarities between this solubilization mechanism and the interaction "ii" discussed in the previous section for the salting-in effect. Interest in hydrotropy to increase the solubility of ROMs for redox flow battery applications is growing in the literature [83–85].

Hydrotropes can be neutral molecules or salts. Ionic hydrotropes usually contain a bulky ion with extensive apolar regions, and a hydrophilic counterion to foster its solubility in water. Thus, ionic liquids are commonly used as hydrotropes [86]. Interestingly, the performance of ionic hydrotropes is directly connected to the solvation energy of its counterion, a phenomenon akin to that discussed in the previous section with the usage of the Hoffmeister series [73]. It is not easy to anticipate which type of hydrotrope works best for a specific ROM. For example, Cheng et al. [84] studied the impact of both neutral (e.g., tert-butanol) and ionic (e.g., sodium p-toluenesulfonate) hydrotropes on the solubility of different ROMs, including an anthraquinone and methyl viologen. Although a general trend could not be identified regarding what type of hydrotrope works best across different types of ROMs, their overall conclusion was that hydrotropy is a useful technique to improve the feasibility of redox flow batteries without altering their electrochemical properties. Another example of hydrotropy for redox flow batteries is the work of Ding et al. that reported an almost 3-fold aqueous solubility increase for a hydroquinone-based ROM using urea as the hydrotrope.

4.4. Considerations and applicability

Table 3 summarizes the three thermodynamic strategies developed in this study to enhance the solubility of redox-active organic molecules (ROMs) in redox flow batteries. It outlines each strategy's main advantages, disadvantages, and practical considerations, providing a concise guide for researchers to select and apply these approaches based on specific system requirements and solubility goals.

Table 3
Analysis of activity coefficient strategies to enhance ROM solubility.

Strategy	Main advantages	Disadvantages	Considerations
Molecular Structure Modifications (Section 3.2)	- Screenable via COSMO-RS - Enables major solubility improvements	- Complex changes may raise synthesis costs - Risk of electrochemical disruption	- Use for robust solubility increase ($>10\times^*$) - Pair with functionalization for best results
Ions Selection (Section 3.3)	- No ROM structural changes needed - Enhances conductivity and electrochemical window - Guided by Hofmeister series	- Risk of ion competition or precipitation - May impair electrochemical performance	- Best for minor solubility adjustments ($<10\times^*$) - Confirm electrolyte compatibility and viscosity
Mixed Solvents (Section 3.4)	- Small additives yield significant effects - No ROM structural changes required - Small co-solvent additions yield notable effects - Guided by COSMO-RS and polarity matching	- Co-solvents may alter electrochemistry or cause side reactions - Possible reduction in electrochemical window or ion conductivity	- Ideal for fine-tuning with minor solubility changes ($<10\times^*$) - Ensure solvent compatibility

* The $10\times$ solubility increase benchmark is a heuristic estimate based on solute solubility comparisons, distinguishing minor from major enhancements.

5. Conclusion

This study systematically examined thermodynamic strategies to enhance the solubility of redox-active organic molecules (ROMs) in electrolyte solutions, with the aim of improving the energy density of redox flow batteries (RFBs). The key approaches focused on reducing melting properties or activity coefficients.

Six strategies were introduced: three aimed at lowering melting properties through molecular asymmetry, and three designed to reduce activity coefficients via structural modifications or solvent additives. COSMO-RS was employed to guide modifications by providing qualitatively accurate predictions of infinite dilution activity coefficients for ROMs in various electrolyte solutions. Therefore, facilitating the assessment of each strategy's effectiveness.

Two strategies—varying alkyl chain lengths (alkylation) or rearranging substituents (substitution pattern)—proved effective in reducing ROM melting temperatures without significantly affecting activity coefficients, as validated by COSMO-RS. This outcome was particularly notable with minor adjustments, such as altering a few carbon atoms or modifying substituents on ROM cores with dispersed charges. These results indicate that straightforward structural changes can enhance energy density across diverse electrolyte systems.

The asymmetry by functionalization strategy can increase ROM solubility by reducing T_m ; however, it could also be associated with changes on activity coefficients or melting enthalpy. When these factors align favorably, this method can markedly improve solubility. However, it also carries risks, such as increased ΔH_m or γ , and may influence electrochemical performance.

Strategies focused on reducing activity coefficients emphasized the critical role of ion management. Small, hydrophilic counterions increased ROMs' aqueous solubilities. The addition of ions to the electrolyte solution can be managed to promote salting-in or reduce salting-out of molecules, guided by the Hofmeister series. ROM's solubility can be enhanced by increasing ions with dispersed charges, such as thiocyanate, or by reducing the concentration of high charge density ions, like sulfonate and magnesium. Additionally, co-solvents were shown to be effective in fine-tuning solubility, with the Scatchard-Hildebrand theory or COSMO-RS guiding the selection of optimal co-solvent and solute combinations to maximize outcomes.

In summary, this study offers a thermodynamic framework comprising six strategies to optimize ROM solubility and RFB energy density. By outlining the strengths and limitations of each approach, accompanied by practical examples, it provides researchers with the tools to select the most appropriate strategy for their specific systems. These insights highlight the importance of thermodynamic principles in advancing the design of next-generation, high-energy-density organic redox flow batteries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Murilo L. Alcantara: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Dinis O. Abranches:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Data curation. **Catarina M.S.S. Neves:** Supervision, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Rubén Rubio-Presa:** Validation, Methodology, Data curation. **Edgar Ventosa:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **João A.P. Coutinho:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT 4.0 in order to increase the readability and correct grammar and typo mistakes. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.117053>.

Data availability

Additional information about sigma profiles' images (S1), and files (S2) are available in the Supplementary material.

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